

THE EFFECT OF INTERNET WEBSITES ON LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The development of internet platforms and websites has had a significant impact on the evolution of the English language and the methods of teaching it. In today's digital world there are many platforms such as Kahoot, Quizlet, Bamboozle, and Flippity and Jeopardy that are helpful and effective ways to teach grammar, vocabulary and improve communicative skills for learners of any age. This article examines how these websites involve all students in tasks and increase their motivation. The study analyzes how effective they are compared to traditional teaching methods and their role in teaching.

Key words: real-life actions, theory, knowledge, long-term memory, brainstorming, motivation, digital learning, engagement, game-based learning.

Introduction: In the era of digital technologies, English has become the most used language worldwide. Moreover, the impact of online platforms has become popular among learners for improving both their cognitive and communicative skills with the help of modern technologies and these websites. The appropriate use of such online platforms makes learning enjoyable and less time-consuming, allowing users to save extra time for using new language skills in the real life. Furthermore, these following platforms also a key aspect of teaching English as a second language for learners as an interactive method by creating friendly and positive competitive atmosphere for them, in comparison with traditional methods in the classroom.

Discussion

The Role of Educational Websites in English Language Teaching

1. Kahoot as an Interactive Assessment Tool

Kahoot is one of the most famous internet platforms for teaching language to learners of any age by interactive methods. It helps teachers to design different types of test methods such as true /false, multiple-choice questions, short quizzes based on grammar rules and structures, vocabulary and even improving their comprehension skills. In addition this platform improves students' speed in finding true answers for questions while working with this. Furthermore, Kahoot will be the best example for formative assessment and immediate feedback, because at the end of the lesson, the platform announces the rankings according to their score, however, if the point of test takers is the same, the platform will count how many seconds they spend on each question. Furthermore, one of the most innovative ways is that students can choose avatars and stickers for their profile on the platform. Popular game-based learning platform that is widely used in English language classrooms to assess students' knowledge in an interactive and motivating way. It allows teachers to design various types of tests, including multiple-choice questions, true/false tasks, and short quizzes based on

grammar rules, vocabulary, and reading comprehension texts. Kahoot is especially effective as a formative assessment tool, as it provides immediate feedback to both teachers and learners. The time-limited questions and competitive scoring system encourage learners to think quickly and stay focused throughout the lesson. Compared to traditional paper-based tests, (Harmer, 2007), that argues Kahoot platform improves communicative competence through interactive teaching in classroom in comparison with traditional methods.

2. Quizlet for Vocabulary Development and Independent Learning

Quizlet is an educational website mainly used among second language learners from all over the world. It offers different types of learning methods, either quiz mode or flashcards, making it easier for students to learn new words. At first they need to open an account using their Google account or iCloud, even they will write their email, after this they need to create flashcard set and write the title of test or quiz above the line, if they want, even there is a line for writing descriptions about new words, For example, if it is new words from German language, Schritte plus a.1.1 book, they can write overall description about book or unit which they are learning. One of the most important ones is detecting source and translation language in the app; after doing it they will write new words on the line, and the app automatically translate it to native language. According to I. S. P. Nation, *'Vocabulary learning requires repetition, retrieval practice and meaningful use'* (Nation, 2013). Quizlet supports Nation's (2013) making the learning process easier by spaced repetition compared to traditional method, also creating fun atmosphere for learners.

3. Flippity as a Tool for Equal Participation and Classroom Management

Flippity is a useful website for educational purposes, not only for teaching foreign language also for science, mathematics and others by guaranteeing fairness among learners. one of the most important features is picking names randomly from the round box, allowing teachers to write all names of students and just press starting button. After that website automatically pick one of the names of students and differentiate it by coloring red, it is helpful when teacher needs to ask new words by order or doing speaking practice with students one by one. Mainly, this website creates fair atmosphere among learners, because as mentioned above there is no need for teachers to choose students to answer the questions, instead, flippity website chooses itself. Moreover, teachers use music or choose colors for names by themselves, making design more friendly. Jack C. Richards & Theodore S. Rodgers (2014) *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching.*, according to him that if the students participate actively and equally, it will have better learning outcomes in the future.

4. Jeopardy for Revision, Competition, and Critical Thinking

This study reveals that Jeopardy is one of the most effective websites for revising all topics and makes learning full of fun and interesting by creating positive atmosphere. Firstly, students need to divide into 2-3 groups and compete by answering questions. The topics depend on the subject itself; if it is related to foreign language, it would be about grammar, vocabulary and 4 skills. each category includes questions ranging from 100 dollars to 500 dollars which depends on the difficulty of the test or teacher will do it vice versa, like 100- is one of the most difficult one starts, but when it comes to 500 – it would be the easiest one, mainly students tend to choose smaller numbers in price thinking it will involve the easier questions compared to other remaining. This website also has timer. When questions appear on the screen, timers start to count backward time while pressure increases learners' focus, so students will try to find answers quicker than normal. James Paul Gee (2003) states that game-based platforms improve critical and strategic thinking by creating friendly atmosphere. This

website supports teamwork, cooperation, collaboration and excitement along with increasing excitement among learners by not choosing specific age category, it is suitable for everyone.

5. Educational Websites and Learner Motivation

There are also two internet websites and applications which make it easier for students to learn a new language by motivating them every day in a daily basis. The first one is, motivation – daily peptelk ‘’ internet platform, which involves motivational speeches from famous people and podcasts which contains useful information and level up for their mindset. Mel Robbins is one who usually interviews with others, giving valuable lessons for others to remain strong, keeping consistency, and all the topics from science to space explorations, themes of podcast are mainly dependent on the guest’s position. The most useful part is that there are no advertisements and other irritating’s, keeping only learning atmosphere, learners also use captions when they are either watching podcast as a video format or just listening to it as a podcast on their way home, school, or university. (Zoltán Dörnyei, 2001) believes that motivation plays an important role in teaching language acquisition. The second one is, I am – daily affirmations app which sends daily quotes or motivational speech to the phone, also users can use it in wide widgets by applying it onto home screen. First, they need to set a timer 3-4 times a day, the app will automatically send daily reminders to keep a positivity for learner. For example, I am confident in my ability to change my life, I am strong, and I am strong, like these types of motivations will change their thoughts, life and attitude towards learning a new language, when they face ups and downs on their way.

6. Bamboozle as a Team-Based Game Platform

Bamboozle is also a type of platform designed for revising vocabulary and grammar structures by working in groups within a class. In this platform learners are divided into two or more groups and answer the questions one by one. Some questions may take longer to answer by affecting practicality of the test on other sites; but when it comes to Bamboozle there is a time limit while answering questions. Teachers will upload all questions with answers together, and the app will sort them automatically within a code, by making less time consuming. First, users need to open an account on this platform by using their google account or iCloud or even just sign in, making it easier to create quizzes, tests or even shuffling games. If it is revision for grammar structures, there will be a true false statement test format in the platform. Besides, users can choose background image, color and music for test by themselves while creating a test, also they can also add descriptions for each answer to the question. This platform encouraged teamwork, fairness, practicality, authenticity and communication between learners. Scott Thornbury (2005) argues that interaction with each other and communication play a crucial role in learning a language. To conclude, bamboozle makes learning interesting and enjoyable by creating friendly atmosphere among learners.

7. Quillbot grammar correction

This website is commonly used for correcting grammar errors while writing ordinary sentences, stories among young learners, also for checking essays and finding errors or inaccuracies in the text. At first, users need to open official account on the website for using this app, after that they will use it for free or with premium for monthly and yearly. The main difference between them is that the free usage has a limit, and users only can use 3-4 time a day, when limit started then it will open only after 5-6 hours for re-usage, on the other hand, there is no limit for premium users, they can use it freely without any limitations in any given time. The website will find grammatical errors in a sentence or text by highlighting them in red and separating them, it will also suggest correct options for users. Ferris, D. R. (2002) argues that giving corrective immediate feedback will improve students’ grammatical

skills by minimizing errors in usage. The most important tool of this website is that it will detect AI and copies from internet sites or programs and give an overall percentage of the text written by humans and how much it is from AI.

8. Vocabulary builder test

This application is one of the most famous and helpful ones among foreign language learners because of its strong engagement and helpfulness. Firstly, users need to open official account and answer following questions like, which language you are studying, your level of knowledge in this language, how much time you devote in a daily basis to working with it and so on. These questions are mainly for knowing current level of knowledge and make it easier for apps to sort vocabulary according to level. For example, if the user's level is A1, the app will only teach and pop-up beginner level words by sorting them into accurate themes, like family, education, body organs, weather, colors. The app encourages regular practice through short quizzes, true and false statements, and interactive tests every day. Additionally, there is a daily reminder for users by sending alerts in a proper given time for encouraging them to learn a vocabulary faster than normal, and needly to say, the statistics are showed that, this application is more effective compared to other traditional methods. This platform reflects the principles of Schmitt's (2000) that word organization according frequency level along with daily quizzes by reminding performance tasks will help to tough lexical resource.

General Advantages of These Platform

According to modern methodology, the following platforms are very helpful and play an important role in learning and teaching a foreign language among learners and teachers. These tools increase effectiveness, motivation and support active participation with proper usage of a language with a given time, in comparison with other traditional methods. As a result, learners will be more confident, engaged in learning and successful in the development of their language skills. James Paul (Gee, 2003) supports the view that games will improve problem solving skills by enhancing engagement and cooperation in learning.

Research question

Will online platforms significantly improve language learning outcomes in comparison with traditional methods?

Research design

The research was conducted over a two-weeks in Uzbek State World Languages University among 3rd year students by dividing them into 2 groups for comparing traditional method for learning new words by using Quizlet, Quiilbot, peptelk Kahoot website for only the second group. Blueprint 3 and dark science books are given to both groups and asked them to read books and learn unknown words by also writing short stories by using these words when the given period finishes, both groups were asked to retell overall meaning of books with unknown words, the findings are showed that the groups who used Quizlet website and Kahoot used for repeating new words, and quillBot for checking their grammar mistakes in storytelling task when they used new words in there, and peptelk for increasing their motivation while studying, the experimental group showed with a high of 48 % in post- test scores compared to pre- tests which were taken before beginning an experiment, they more likely to remember what was the book is about in each page, and did less mistakes, by performing better in comparison with students who used traditional method and engaged only 25% by tending to forget them. These results showed that digital platforms contribute more effective teaching and learning environments in education.

The participants who took part in research in 3 weeks in UzSWLU.

General Advantages of Internet Platforms

It offers several advantages.

- Increasing motivation
- Immediate feedback
- Cooperation with group
- Improves communicative competence
- Less time for learning
- Higher engagement level among learners

Limitations of the Study

However, these following digital platforms have some limitations by limiting the number of participants and usage time by promoting weekly, monthly and yearly subscriptions by paying a certain amount of money or promoting advertisements in any time during learning process which interrupts learners. Consequently, there will be cellular data platforms, because some of the platforms require better network lines if users want to use them faster.

Conclusion

Educational websites such as Kahoot, Quizlet, Flippity, Jeopardy, motivational websites, Bamboozle, QuillBot and vocabulary builder apps play a crucial role in teaching modern English. They offer many useful and innovative ways for teaching and learning a foreign language among learners, with different types of methods in effective ways. Therefore, internet-based educational tools should be considered as an effective and crucial component of a modern English language education.

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